

NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MOBIL ILOVA YARATISH

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining axborot-kommunikatsion va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni ta'lim tizimiga joriy etishga bag'ishlangan Qaror, farmon va nutqlaridan kelib chiqib bugungi kunda ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar, ma'lumotlar bazasi resurslari hamda dasturiy vositalarga bo'lgan ehtiyojning ortishi uni ishlab chiqarish va ta'limda qo'llash masalasi dolzarbligini ko'rsatadi. Ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimlarining umumiy tushunchalari, ularning turlari, klassifikatsiyasi, ma'lumotlar bazasining modellari va ularni me'yorlashtirish shakllari, ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlaydigan tillarning komponentalari hamda so'rovlarni tashkil etish texnologiyasi, shuningdek bilimlar bazasi bilan ishlash tartibi xususida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Zamonaviy kompyuterlardan foydalangan holda yangi axborot texnologiyalari asosida ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash bilan akademik litsey va kasb-hunar kollejlari o'quvchilari, shuningdek, institut va universitet talabalari keng shug'ullanmoqdalar. Hozirgi kunda kompyuterdan foydalanuvchi har bir kishi WORD matn muharriri yordamida matnlarni qayta ishlashni, ya'ni kerakli ko'rinishda formatlashni, chop etishni va bir qancha nusxa olishni qiynalmasdan amalga oshiradi. Hisoblashlar bilan bog'liq masalalarni EXCELda, taqdimot jarayonlarini PowerPointda amalga oshirish ko'pchilikka ma'lum. Xuddi shuningdek, internet sahifalariga ma'lumotlarni kiritish uchun HTML tilidan yoki FrontPage programmasidan foydalanish kerakligini bilasiz. Kompyuter bilan bog'liq va kompyuter yordamida juda tez amalga oshirish mumkin bo'lgan shunday masalalar turkumi mavjudki, ular bilan har kuni va har qadamda ro'baro' bo'ladi. Bunday masalalar turkumi ma'lumotlar bazasi deb ataladi.

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Bugungi kunda Android operatsion tizimi mobil qurilmalar sohasida eng keng tarqalgan. Android ochiq manbali kod va Google Siyosat tufayli o'z mahsulotlari uchun mobil qurilma ishlab chiqaruvchilariga android

platformasini bepul ishlatishiga imkon beradigan mashhurligini oshirdi. Android foydalaniladi, chunki Samsung, HTC, Sony, Huawei kabi yirik mobil qurilmalari foydalaniladi.

Nodavlat o'quv markazlari tizimi platformasining mobil ilovasi Android operatsion tizimi uchun ishlab chiqildi. Bunda foydalanuvchi dastlab platforma tizimida ro'yxatdan o'tishi zarur. Foydalanuvchi platformada ro'yxatdan o'tishi ichun maxsus oynada (1-rasm) quyidagi ma'lumotlarni kiritishi zarur:

1. Foydalanuvchi ismi;
2. Foydalanuvchi Familiyasi;
3. Foydalanuvchining otasining ismi;
4. Foydalanuvchi telefon raqami;
5. Tizimdan foydalanish uchun Login;
6. Tizimdan foydalanish uchun foydalanuvchi paroli.

1-rasm. Foydalanuvchining platforma tizimida ro'yxatdan o'tish oynasi.

Foydalanuvchi ro'yxatdan o'tkanidan so'ng autorizatsiyadan o'tib (2-rasm), platformada yaratilgan barcha xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

2-rasm. Foydalanuvchining platforma tizimida autorizatsiyadan o'tish oynasi.

Foydalanuvchining platforma tizimida autorizatsiyadan o'tish oynasini yaratish uchun quyidagi dastur kodidan yozildi:

```
import UIKit
import MBProgressHUD
class HomeController: UIViewController {
```



```
var heightSize:CGFloat = 0.0
var widthSize:CGFloat = 0.0
var byEmailTextField:Bool = false
@IBOutlet weak var customBar:UIView!
@IBOutlet weak var subCustomBar:UIView!
@IBOutlet weak var barButton:UIButton!
@IBOutlet weak var sendButton:UIButton!
@IBOutlet weak var revealButton:UIButton!
@IBOutlet weak var segmentControl:UISegmentedControl!
@IBOutlet weak var forUserNameTextFieild:NSLayoutConstraint!
@IBOutlet weak var forEmailTextFieild:NSLayoutConstraint!
@IBOutlet weak var userNameTextField:UITextField!
@IBOutlet weak var userPhoneTextField:UITextField!
@IBOutlet weak var loginTextField:UITextField!
@IBOutlet weak var passwordTextField:UITextField!
@IBOutlet weak var emailTextField:UITextField!
@IBOutlet weak var scrollView:UIScrollView!
override func viewDidLoad() {
    super.viewDidLoad()
    let id = UserDefaults.standard.string(forKey: "1")
    if id == "1" {
        let vc = self.storyboard?.instantiateViewController(identifier:
"SchoolViewController") as! SchoolViewController
        self.navigationController?.pushViewController(vc, animated: true)
    } else {
        let revealViewController = self.revealViewController()
        revealButton.addTarget(revealViewController, action:
#selector(SWRevealViewController.revealToggle(_:)), for: .touchUpInside)
self.view.addGestureRecognizer(self.revealViewController().panGestureRecogn
izer())
        self.revealViewController()?.rearViewRevealWidth = 200
        self.customBar.layer.borderWidth = 3
        self.customBar.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
        self.customBar.layer.cornerRadius = 35.0
        self.customBar.clipsToBounds = true
        self.subCustomBar.layer.borderWidth = 3
```



```
self.subCustomBar.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:255/255,
green:255/255, blue:255/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.subCustomBar.layer.cornerRadius = 20.0
self.subCustomBar.clipsToBounds = true
self.revealButton.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.revealButton.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.revealButton.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
self.revealButton.clipsToBounds = true
let font = UIFont.boldSystemFont(ofSize: 18)
let normalAttribute: [NSAttributedString.Key: Any] = [.font: font,
.foregroundColor: UIColor(red:230/255, green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1)]
self.segmentControl.setTitleTextAttributes(normalAttribute, for: .normal)
let selectedAttribute: [NSAttributedString.Key: Any] = [.font: font,
.foregroundColor: UIColor.white]
segmentControl.setTitleTextAttributes(selectedAttribute, for: .selected)
self.segmentControl.layer.borderWidth = 2
self.segmentControl.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.userNameTextField.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.userNameTextField.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.userNameTextField.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
self.userNameTextField.clipsToBounds = true
self.userPhoneTextField.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.userPhoneTextField.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.userPhoneTextField.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
self.userPhoneTextField.clipsToBounds = true
self.loginTextField.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.loginTextField.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.loginTextField.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
self.loginTextField.clipsToBounds = true
self.passwordTextField.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.passwordTextField.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
```



```

self.passwordTextField.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
self.passwordTextField.clipsToBounds = true
self.emailTextField.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.emailTextField.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.emailTextField.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
self.emailTextField.clipsToBounds = true
self.sendButton.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.sendButton.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.sendButton.layer.cornerRadius = 20.0
self.sendButton.clipsToBounds = true
self.heightSize = self.view.frame.size.height
self.widthSize = self.view.frame.size.width
self.scrollView.contentSize = CGSize(width: self.widthSize, height:
600)
}
}
@IBAction func printInTextField(){
let str = self.emailTextField.text
self.byEmailTextField = (str?.contains("@"))!
}
@IBAction func bySegmentControl(){
if self.segmentControl.selectedSegmentIndex == 0 {
self.userNameTextField.text = ""
self.userPhoneTextField.text = ""
self.loginTextField.text = ""
self.passwordTextField.text = ""
self.emailTextField.text = ""
self.userNameTextField.isHidden = true
self.userPhoneTextField.isHidden = true
self.emailTextField.isHidden = true
self.forUserNameTextFiell.constant = 0.0
self.forEmailTextFiell.constant = 0.0
} else {
self.userNameTextField.text = ""
self.userPhoneTextField.text = ""

```



```
self.loginTextField.text = ""
self.passwordTextField.text = ""
self.emailTextField.text = ""
self.userNameTextField.isHidden = false
self.userPhoneTextField.isHidden = false
self.emailTextField.isHidden = false
self.forUserNameTextFiell.constant = 34
self.forEmailTextFiell.constant = 38
}
}
func allertShow(message:String, counter:Int) {
    if counter == 1 {
        self.userNameTextField.text = ""
        self.userPhoneTextField.text = ""
        self.loginTextField.text = ""
        self.passwordTextField.text = ""
        self.emailTextField.text = ""
    }
    let alertCont = UIAlertController(title: title, message: message,
preferredStyle: UIAlertController.Style.alert)
    let action = UIAlertAction(title: "OK", style: UIAlertAction.Style.default,
handler: {(_) in
    })
    alertCont.addAction(action)
    self.present(alertCont, animated: true, completion: nil)

}
@IBAction func sendRestHelper(){
    if self.segmentControl.selectedSegmentIndex == 1 {
        if (self.userNameTextField.text == "") || (self.userPhoneTextField.text
== "") || (self.emailTextField.text == "") || (self.loginTextField.text == "") ||
(self.passwordTextField.text == "") {
            self.allertShow(message: "Barcha maydonlarni to`ldiring", counter: 2)
        } else if self.byEmailTextField == true{
            let params =
["user_name":self.userNameTextField.text!,"user_phone":self.userPhoneTextFiel
d.text!,
"log":self.loginTextField.text!,
```



```

"pas":self.passwordTextField.text!,"email":self.emailTextField.text!,"login":RestH
elper.log["login"], "password":RestHelper.log["password"]]
    MBProgressHUD.showAdded(to: self.view, animated: true)
    RestHelper.registrationFunction(params: params as! [String : String],
completion: {jsonText,isSuccess in
    if isSuccess {
        MBProgressHUD.hide(for: self.view, animated: true)
        self.allertShow(message: "Siz registratsiyadan muvofaqiyatli
o`ttinigiz. Login oynasiga o'ting", counter: 1)
    }
    }, failure: { (jsonText, isFailure) in
        MBProgressHUD.hide(for: self.view, animated: true)
        if jsonText == "The network connection was lost." {
            self.allertShow(message: jsonText, counter: 1)
        } else {
            self.allertShow(message: "No internet connections", counter:
1)
        }
    })
} else {
    self.allertShow(message: "Email maydoni xato to`ldirilgan",counter:
2)
}
}
else {
    if (self.loginTextField.text == "") || (self.passwordTextField.text == "") {
self.allertShow(message: "Barcha maydonlarni to`ldiring", counter: 2)
    } else {
        let params = ["log":self.loginTextField.text!,
"pas":self.passwordTextField.text!,"login":RestHelper.log["login"],
"password":RestHelper.log["password"]]
        MBProgressHUD.showAdded(to: self.view, animated: true)
        RestHelper.autorizatsiyaFunction(params: params as! [String :
String], completion: {jsonText,isSuccess in
            if isSuccess {
                MBProgressHUe(for: self.view, animated: true)
                if jsonText == "false" {

```


Platformada mavjud o'quv markazlar ro'yxati oynasini yaratish uchun quyidagi dastur kodidan yozildi:

```
import UIKit
import MBProgressHUD
import SDWebImage
class SchoolViewController: UIViewController {
    var heightSize:CGFloat = 0.0
    var widthSize:CGFloat = 0.0
    var topSchoolArray=[TopSchoolModel]()
    @IBOutlet weak var SchoolTableView:UITableView!
    @IBOutlet weak var revealButton:UIButton!
    @IBOutlet weak var refreshButton:UIButton!
    @IBOutlet weak var barButton:UIButton!
    @IBOutlet weak var customBar:UIView!
    @IBOutlet weak var subCustomBar:UIView!
    override func viewDidLoad() {
        super.viewDidLoad()
        self.topSchoolArray.removeAll()
        heightSize = self.view.frame.size.height
        widthSize = self.view.frame.size.width
        let revealViewController = self.revealViewController()
        revealButton.addTarget(revealViewController,
        self.revealViewController()?.rearViewRevealWidth = 200
        self.revealButton.layer.borderWidth = 3
        self.revealButton.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
        self.revealButton.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
        self.revealButton.clipsToBounds = true
        self.refreshButton.layer.borderWidth = 3
        self.refreshButton.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
        self.refreshButton.layer.cornerRadius = 15.0
        self.refreshButton.clipsToBounds = true
        self.customBar.layer.borderWidth = 3
        self.customBar.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:230/255,
green:112/255, blue:18/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
        self.customBar.layer.cornerRadius = 35.0
```



```
self.customBar.clipsToBounds = true
self.subCustomBar.layer.borderWidth = 3
self.subCustomBar.layer.borderColor = UIColor(red:255/255, green:255/255,
blue:255/255, alpha: 1).CGColor
self.subCustomBar.layer.cornerRadius = 20.0
self.subCustomBar.clipsToBounds = true
self.sendRestHelper()
}
override func viewWillAppear(_ animated: Bool) {
    super.viewWillAppear(animated)
    heightSize = self.view.frame.size.height
    widthSize = self.view.frame.size.width
}
func sendRestHelper() {
    self.topSchoolArray.removeAll()
    self.SchoolTableView.reloadData()
    let params = ["login":RestHelper.log["login"],
"password":RestHelper.log["password"]]
    MBProgressHUD.showAdded(to: self.SchoolTableView, animated: true)
    RestHelper.topSchoolsFunction(params: params as! [String : String],
completion: {jsonArray,isSuccess in
        if isSuccess {
            MBProgressHUD.hide(for: self.SchoolTableView, animated: true)
            for js in jsonArray {
                self.topSchoolArray.append(js)
            }
            self.SchoolTableView.reloadData()
        }
    }, failure: { (jsonText, isFailure) in
        MBProgressHUD.hide(for: self.SchoolTableView, animated: true)
        if jsonText == "The network connection was lost." {
            self.alertShow(message: jsonText, counter: 1)
        } else {
            self.alertShow(message: "No internet connections", counter: 1)
        }
    })
})
```



```

}
func showAlertShow(message:String, counter:Int) {
    let alertCont = UIAlertController(title: title, message: message,
preferredStyle: UIAlertController.Style.alert)
    let action = UIAlertAction(title: "OK", style: UIAlertAction.Style.default,
handler: {(_) in
    })
    alertCont.addAction(action)
    self.present(alertCont, animated: true, completion: nil)
}
@IBAction func refreshData(){

```


4-rasm. O'quv markaz to'g'risida statistik va geografik ma'lumotlar.

5-rasm. O'quv markazda tashkil qilingan kurslar to'g'risida ma'lumot va online kurslarga registratsiyani amalga oshirish.

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